

The Effect Of Human Resource Management Practices On Employees' Retention In King Saud University

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Abstract

This study aims to investigate the effect of HRM Practices on employees' retention in King Saud University. The study is a cross-sectional descriptive research. It utilizes a quantitative approach. It will prove the cause and effect relationship between employee retention and the independent factors, i.e. empowerment, training, compensation and appraisal. A random sampling method was used to identify a sample for the study. The survey questionnaire was distributed through an online survey. After removing incomplete submissions, a total of 440 respondents sent their to-questionnaire- Responses. All of them were from King Saud University . A structured questionnaire is used for data collection which covers 5 main independent variables. It contains 26 items . It consists of two parts, section A is general information, while Section B consists of questions about 5 factors which have an impact on employee retention: compensation and rewards, working conditions, training and development, employee empowerment and appraisal system. All variables were correlated positively and significantly at $p < .001$). All variables predicted and positively affected employees' retention in King Saud University.

Keywords: Human Resources Management Practices, Compensation and rewards, Working conditions, Training and Development, Employee empowerment, Employee Retention.

Introduction

Employee retention (ER) is considered as one of the most popular researched issues in the field of human resource management (HRM) (Bibi, Ahmad & Majid, 2018). Effective human resources management (HRM) through a series of recruitment, selection, development and rewards could ensure employees are taken care of, harness their potential and retain them for long term (Hassan, 2022).

There is a growing global interest in matters of recruitment and staff retention in higher education institutions (Hassan, 2022). Retaining talented academicians is important to ensure the ability of educational

institutions to respond to changing dynamics of teaching and learning delivery (Boudlaie et al., 2020). The main purpose of retention is to prevent competent employees from leaving the organization as this could have adverse effects on productivity and service delivery (Wambui, 2014).

Human Resources Management Practices (HRM)

HRM include the systems and policies that influence the behaviour, performance and attitudes of employees who are considered the most valuable assets of any business organisation (Alajlani & Yesufu, 2022). Reina & Scarozza, (2021) define HRM practice as a strategic and tactical way to

manage, develop, retain, motivate and obtained employees' commitment. The importance of HRM lies in its strategic plan (Boselie et al., 2021).

Effective HRM practice will influence employees' behaviours hence positively showing business performance (Beijer, Peccei, Van Veldhoven & Paauwe, 2021). HRM practice are classified into five main domains (Alajlani & Yesufu, 2022):

Compensation and rewards

Rewards and compensations are tangible and financial returns earned by an employee (Nazir, et al. 2013). compensation of faculty is conceptualized as the pay which they receive on monthly basis from institutions (Tessema & Soeters, 2006). Irshad and Afridi (2011) mentioned that it is a key role that leads to employee retention in the organisation's rewards. Ramlall (2013) studied the impacts of compensation on staff retention and found a significant relationship between them. Moreover, Nawab and Bhatti (2013); Saeed et al, (2013); Ramlall (2013) also found a significant relationship between compensation on employees' retention.

Working conditions (WC)

WCs construct is defined as the degree to which employees consider the workplace physically safe (Xuecheng ,Iqbal & Saina, 2022). Maintaining employee well-being and providing a safe working environment is one of the main HRM practices because it is directly related to organizational performance, individual well-being and contributing to the success of the organization (Xuecheng et al., 2022). Attractive and clean environment encourages individual employees to complete their work effectively and is expected to have positive impact on employees' retention and commitment. Some examples of work environment

indicators include supervisor support (Stirpe and Zárrega-Oberty, 2017), physical working conditions (Richards et al., 1994), social worker support (Haggins, 2011), and helping behaviours during decision-making (Subramaniam and Mia, 2001).

Training and Development (TD)

Through training and development (Aladağ et al., 2022; Koçak, 2021), employees could acquire new skills and experience which enable them to perform the task effectively and efficiently. Investment in training and development programmes is a critical factor in retaining employees. Training and development programmes deal with the employees' skills and competencies, enabling them to positively respond to various challenges the organisations face (Rhee et al., 2014). Training is the fundamental source of competitive advantage and employee retention (Yamin, 2019). Past studies have found a positive relationship between training and development with commitment (Ahmad et al., 2017), employee performance (Sinha et al., 2010), and job satisfaction (Bibi et al., 2018). Others include employee retention (Lee, 2005), employee commitment (Ahmad et al., 2017), and employees' intentions to stay (Chew and Chan, 2008).

Performance appraisal (PA)

PA is the process of evaluating the employees' performance and judging their tasks based on a set of established standards (Fahim, 2018). Feedback, selection, communication, performance evaluation, and periodic analysis are key components of the performance assessment (Pisak et al., 2020). Employee feedback encourages behavioral shaping and improves learning that helps driving retention and performance (Haider et al., 2015).

Employee empowerment (EE)

EE includes the various ways in which organisations empower its employees with a certain level of autonomy and control in their job (Yin, Wang, & Lu, 2019). Empowerment also aims at providing employees with the mechanisms for making important decisions (Alajlani & Yesufu, 2022; Özkan Hıdıroğlu & Tanrıöğen, 2022; Sari, 2022).

Employee Retention (ER)

Employee retention refers to policies and programmes aimed at ensuring that the organization keeps its productive employees for a long period (Armstrong, 2009). Rubel, Kee & Rimi (2021) define ER as an organization's ability to keep its employees. In order for an organization to achieve its goals, it is important to retain talented employees. Samuel and Chipunza, (2009) stated that retaining skilled employees would be a great concern for firms as the level of staff turnover increases globally.

Statement of the problem

The role of education in economic development is undeniable important and human resources are the bloodline of the education sector. Human resources are said to be the most vital assets of any institution. Educational institutions seek to retain efficient and experienced workers. This step is likely to have a positive effect on the overall performance of the institution. There is a growing global interest in matters of recruitment and staff retention in higher education institutions.

Research Questions

This study raised the following research questions:

1. What is the impact of compensation and rewards on ER?

2. What is the impact of working conditions on ER?

3. What is the impact of training and development on ER?

4. What is the impact of performance appraisal on ER?

5. What is the impact of employee empowerment on ER?

Purpose of the Study

This study aims to investigate the effect of HRM Practices on employees' retention in King Saud University.

Significant of Study

It is expected that the findings of this study will add a vital value to the growing body of the existing knowledge in Human Resources Management (HRM) Practices and how they affect employee retention. researchers and management of higher education institutions are likely to benefit from the results of this study. Future researchers are likely to make use of any related knowledge and information that can be used to improve research on the topic of Human Resources Management (HRM) Practices and how they affect employee retention.

Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: Compensation and rewards has a positive impact on ER.

Hypothesis 2: Working conditions have a positive impact on ER.

Hypothesis 3: Training and development have a positive impact on ER.

Hypothesis 4: Performance appraisal has a positive impact on ER.

Hypothesis 5: Employee empowerment has a positive impact on ER.

A conceptual framework is showed in figure 1.

Fig.1. Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

Source: Alajlani, S., & Yesufu, L.O. (2022). The impact of human resource practices on employee retention: A study of three private higher educational institutions in the United Arab Emirates. *SA Journal of Human Resource Management/SA Tydskrif vir Mens like hulpbronbestuur*, 20(0), a1823.

Methodology

Research Design

The study is a cross-sectional descriptive research. It utilizes a quantitative approach. It will prove the cause and effect relationship between employee retention and the independent factors, i.e. empowerment, training, compensation and appraisal.

Participants

A random sampling method was used to identify a sample for the study. The survey questionnaire was distributed through an online survey. After removing incomplete submissions, a total of 440 respondents sent their to-questionnaire- Reponses. All of them were from King Saud University .

Data Collection instrument

A structured questionnaire is used for data collection which covers 5 main independent variables. It contains 26 items . It consists of two parts, section A is general information, while Section B consists of questions about 5 factors which have an impact on employee retention: compensation and rewards, working conditions, training and development, employee empowerment and appraisal system.

Reliability and validity

Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value shows that all reflective constructs have AVE values ≥ 0.50 . Hence the CV is valid and acceptable All indicators that measure constructs have met the conditions of CV. Moreover, the results of the Composite Reliability (CR) data show that all values were above 0.8 .This refers to high reliability. The results of Cronbach's Alpha (CA), show high reliability. The data can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1. Convergent Validity and Reliability

	AVE	CR	CA
CR	0.744	0.812	0.731
WC	0.754	0.826	0.722
TD	0.729	0.855	0.733
PA	0.734	0.886	0.751
EE	0.726	0.894	0.724

AVE Average Variance Extracted; CR Composite Reliability; CA Cronbach's Alpha

Pilot Testing

Using the self-report , structured questionnaire , pilot testing has been conducted to ensure that respondents understand all items.

Data Analysis

Data were analysed using IBM SPSS version 18. Invalid questionnaires, including those that were incomplete or provided the same response for all items or with many missing values, were eliminated. Pearson correlation(R) and multiple regression (MRA) were used to analyze data .

Results

Table 2. Correlation of study variables

Variable	1	2	3	4	5	6
CR						.344***
WC						.332***
TD						.321***
PA						.384***
EE						.389***
ER						-
Average	16.3	18.6	17.5	16.7	17.2	16.9
STD	2.51	2.12	2.00	2.16	2.11	2.18
skewness	.54	.40	.43	.47	.39	.38
kurtosis	.59	.70	.61	.59	.54	.58

Correlation of research variables

The mean and STD of the variables were calculated, and skewness and kurtosis were calculated and presented in table 2 to check whether the multivariate normal distribution assumption was satisfied. As a result of the correlation analysis, all variables were correlated positively and significantly at $p < .001$). The absolute values of skewness and kurtosis do not exceed 3 and 10, respectively, it can be judged that the normal distribution assumption is satisfied, and kurtosis ranged from .11 to .83, indicating that there was no problem with multivariate normality.

Note: CR= Compensation and rewards, WC= Working conditions, TD= Training and development, PA= Performance appraisal, EE= Employee empowerment ,ER= employee retention *** $p < .001$.

Prediction

Results presented in table 3 show that the independent variables (CR, WC, TD, PA and EE) when put together yielded a coefficient of multiple regression (R) of (.633) and a multiple correlation square of (.644). This shows that 64.4% of the total

variance in employee retention of those who participated in the study is accounted for by the combination of CR, WC, TD, PA and EE. Table 4 indicates that the analysis of variance of the multiple regression data produced an F-ratio value significant at 0.01 level ($F(2, 434) = 20.645$; $P < 0.01$).

Table 3. The regression results of the Predictor Variables and the Outcome Measure

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change statistics				
					R Square change	F Change	Df1	Df2	Sig. F change
1	.721a	.633	.644	4.02644	.550	28.962	5	434	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), CR, WC, TD, PA and EE

b. IV: ER

Table 4 Summary of Multiple Regression Analysis

ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	795.803	5	159.160	20.645	.000a
Residual	970.888	434	2.237		
Total	1766.691	439			

a. Predictors: (Constant), CR, WC, TD, PA and EE

b. IV: ER

As shown in table 5, PU, PEOU contributed to the prediction of BI and beta weights were as follows: PU ($b = 0.394$, $t = 4.243$; $P < 0.01$), and PEOU ($b = 0.372$, $t = 4.074$, $P < 0.01$).

Table 5. Relative Contribution of Predictor Variables to the Prediction of Outcome Measure.

Coefficients a

Model	Unstandarized coefficients		Standarized coefficients	t	sig
	B	Std error	Beta		
1 (constant)	9.778	2.822		3.441	.003
CR	0.379	0.091	0.394	4.243	.000
WC	0.363	0.090	0.372	4.074	.000

TD	0.368	0.092	0.374	4.076	.000
PA	0.380	0.092	0.395	4.248	.000
EE	0.369	0.089	0.375	4.201	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), CR, WC, TD, PA and EE

b. IV: ER

Discussion

The first IV is CR. It has a value of t statistics above the accepted benchmark of (+2) which is 4.243, and a significant value of (0.000) which less than (0.05). As for the beta value, the table shows (0.394). This value means that there is a positive relationship between (CR) and (ER). This value also shows that for each unit increase in (CR), there is a 39.4% increase in ER. The significant value of (0.000) is less than 0.05. This shows that there is a significant positive relationship between the independent variable of (CR) and the dependent variable of (ER). Therefore, hypothesis (H1) is supported. It states that "Compensation and rewards has a positive impact on ER". Reward and compensation practices cause to increase employee retention among the employees (Aleem & Bowra, 2020; Hanai & Pallangyo, 2020). According to Nazir et al. (2013) rewards to motivate the employees to perform beyond expectation and encourage them to stay in the organization.

The second IV is WC. It has a value of t statistics above the accepted benchmark of (+2) which is 4.074, and a significant value of (0.000) which less than (0.05). As for the beta value, the table shows (0.372). This value means that there is a positive relationship between (WC) and (ER). This value also shows that for each unit increase in (WC), there is a 37.2% increase in ER. The significant value of (0.000) is less than 0.05. This shows that there is a significant positive relationship between the independent variable of (WC) and the

dependent variable of (ER). Therefore, hypothesis (H2) is supported. It states that "Working conditions have a positive impact on ER". This means that having an acceptable and comfortable working atmosphere would satisfy and retain employees in the organization. According to Gaceri (2015), WCs that relate to health and safety standards are likely to increase work performance and at the same time reduce the risk of accidents, illness or disabilities. Therefore, it may result in more employee retention.

The third IV is TD. It has a value of t statistics above the accepted benchmark of (+2) which is 4.076, and a significant value of (0.000) which less than (0.05). As for the beta value, the table shows (0.374). This value means that there is a positive relationship between (TD) and (ER). This value also shows that for each unit increase in (TD), there is a 37.4% increase in ER. The significant value of (0.000) is less than 0.05. This shows that there is a significant positive relationship between the independent variable of (TD) and the dependent variable of (ER). Therefore, hypothesis (H3) is supported. It states that "Training and development have a positive impact on ER". That is to say that organizations that concentrate their efforts on investment in training and development end up retaining their key employees (Wambui, 2014). Training at the workplace improves work efficiency, develops work interests, satisfies employees and strengthens the commitment to the organization leading to retention of employees (Hanif, 2013).

The fourth IV is PA. It has a value of t statistics above the accepted benchmark of (+2) which is 4.248, and a significant value of (0.000) which less than (0.05). As for the beta value, the table shows (0.395). This value means that there is a positive relationship between (PA) and (ER). This value also shows that for each unit increase in (PA), there is a 39.5% increase in ER. The significant value of (0.000) is less than 0.05. This shows that there is a significant positive relationship between the independent variable of (PA) and the dependent variable of (ER). Therefore, hypothesis (H4) is supported. It states that "Performance appraisal has a positive impact on ER". This finding goes in the same line with that Alajlani & Yesufu (2022). These authors state that performance appraisal has a positive impact on employee retention

The fifth IV is EE. It has a value of t statistics above the accepted benchmark of (+2) which is 4.201, and a significant value of (0.000) which less than (0.05). As for the beta value, the table shows (0.375). This value means that there is a positive relationship between (EE) and (ER). This value also shows that for each unit increase in (EE), there is a 37.5% increase in ER. The significant value of (0.000) is less than 0.05. This shows that there is a significant positive relationship between the independent variable of (EE) and the dependent variable of (ER). Therefore, hypothesis (H5) is supported. It states that "Employee empowerment has a positive impact on ER". This finding goes in the same line with that Alajlani & Yesufu (2022) and Bibi, Ahmad & Majid (2018). These authors state that Employee empowerment has a positive impact on employee retention

Samuel & Chipunza (2009) in their study specified staff compensation, training and development, performance management,

employee engagement and work-life balance as the most important HRM practices that play a vital role in ER in modern day organizations.

Conclusion and recommendation

HRM Practices are the vital backbone in every academic institution. To retain skilled and qualified employees, good HRM practices must be applied across the globe so organizational effectiveness can be improved. Coaching and mentoring are seen as the most real methods of training facilities. If any educational institution wishes to ensure that CR practices enhance employee retention, then it is crucial for the management to adopt measures to strengthen the perceived fairness of CR practices among the employees. By investing in the appropriate training programs, a company will gain benefits such as increased productivity, reduced employee turnover, and decreased need for constant supervision. It is suggested that further studies and other mixed methods both quantitative and qualitative aimed at gathering greater insights to more specific HRM practices.

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